

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

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MILESTONE 7

KICK-OFF WORKSHOP FOR STEĆCI LABS MANAGERS
AND LOCAL PARTNERS FROM THE CONSORTIUM
TRANSFERRING THE DESCRIPTION OF METHODS
FOR STEĆCI LABS

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MILESTONE 7 Kick-off workshop for Stećci Labs managers and local partners from the consortium transferring the description of methods for Stećci Labs

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The research and co-creation done in WP5 enables social-needs-based and community-driven innovation by involving multi-stakeholders from the quadruple-helix. Milestone 7 *"STECCI PROJECT – Kick-off workshop for Stećci Labs managers and local partners from the consortium transferring the description of methods for Stećci Labs"* is based on the findings generated in T5.1 and compiled in the D.5.1 (M7).

To enable the needed participatory approach for a successful stakeholder engagement on-site of the five STECCI pilots, an online workshop of three hours with the assigned STECCI lab managers took place in April 2024 (M8). The following chapters describe the train-the-trainer workshop and presents the practical toolkit and its use for all co-creation and citizen science activities in T5.2 and beyond.

WP5 leader Centre for Social Innovation (WP5) implemented all efforts, supported by a series of internal co-design sessions (implemented during task meetings) together with the consortium partners involved in T5.1.

2. KICK-OFF OF STECCI SOCIAL LABS WITH A TRAIN-THE-TRAINER WORKSHOP

In month 7, the train-the-trainer workshop on 15th of April (M8) set the scene for social lab events and workshops in T5.2 (M8-21). It built on the methodology presented in the deliverable 5.1, which was submitted in M7. The train-the-trainer workshop provided guidance and set the scene for the lab activities in the follow-up task 5.2 collaboratively working on the socially inclusive valorisation building opportunities for social innovation and the sensitive exploitation of stecci in the context of cultural tourism.

Fig. 1: Timeline of the co-creation process in T5.1 and T5.2 including the train-the-trainer workshop

2.1 THE WORKSHOP

On 15th of April the official inauguration of the STECCI Social Labs took place virtually joined by in total of 11 participants from five partner institutions, including Center for Social Innovation representing the STECCI consortium partners implementing a social lab or citizen science workshop series.

Fig. 2: Screenshot from the inauguration meeting

During the train-the-trainer workshop, the general outline and set-up of the STECCI social labs, the logistics of the local kick-off events and a pre-analysed set of methods for co-creation were showcased. STECCI internal participants of this workshop are obliged to follow guidelines and to do a knowledge transfer to their social local lab managers for the kick-off workshops participants and/or core participants in the regional language.

These methods are based on previous exploratory interviews and co-design session with the consortium. The list of methods will be further enhanced due to the development of the STECCI Social Labs. At moment, there are 14 methods analysed against the background of the five pilot project cases. All 14 methods suggested for the different phases of co-creation or collaborative research. Beside the World Café, which comes from Art of Hosting, all other methods can be chosen due to local needs.

Fig. 2: Methods in the research phases of the STECCI labs

Methods cover creative, interactive, reflective, or evidence-gathering approaches and formats to foster pilot activities. These activities follow the rationale on how local communities can benefit from cultural heritage, the role of citizen science in deepening people's relationship with stećci and how participatory approaches can promote the strengthening of place meanings. The involvement of citizens, especially young people and children, and the collaboration with the cultural and creative industries should increase citizens' scientific literacy and raise awareness of sustainable impacts which will be outlined in the final policy brief for sustainable stećci tourism at later stage of the project. In any case, only the method World Café is obligatory to all STECCI Social Labs in the kick-off phase to support a needs assessment the social lab building in group work.

Fig. 3: Methods in the research phases of the STECCI labs

The stakeholder engagement in STECCI is a continuous, voluntary activity providing an open and active dialogue between diverse stakeholder groups. STECCI takes advantage of the so-called quadruple helix (HQ) concept. Consortium partners implementing a co-creation activity in T5.2 were briefed during the train-the-trainer workshop to put a focus and extra effort to take care of stakeholder's needs and to co-design at least some of the potential social lab activities together with participants during the kick-off phase to ensure a high degree of participation in the double sense of the term.

Center for Social Innovation will further support process in the STECCI Social Labs in T5.2 (and beyond in WP4) and the regular assessment of quality and participatory standards needed to gain full potential of this social intervention, such as the stringent application of a tailor-made code of conduct in the STECCI Social Labs.

2.2 THE TOOLKIT

The toolkit can be found on EMDESK cloud database with materials that enable pilot partners to implement the STECCI Social Labs and citizen science activities in the five pilots.

These materials are available and will be updated by WP5 leader and these consortium partner organisations hosting co-creation or collaborative research activities:

- **STEC CI SLs Kick-off Planner**, this planner serves as a detailed roadmap for the Social Labs event planning, which will be used to fill-in the information requested by ZSI within the planner. Filled-in templates will be uploaded in each pilot folder on EMDESK.
- **STEC CI Informed Consent**, which needs to be translated into the local languages and once it is signed from all the participants, uploaded in the *Informed Consent Signed Folder*. This can be found in each EMDESK pilot folder. Ideally, informed consent is sent

to the confirmed participants hand in hand with a friendly reminder – best six weeks before the event.

- **STECCI Flyer Digital** is the flyer of the project, which can be used digitally or printed.
- **STECCI Roll up** (of the STECCI project) is available with English translation and must be printed on site.
- **STECCI Social Lab invitation**, this is the invitation to be sended to the stakeholders that you aim to invite in your events, please update it with the specific information for each pilot, instructions are given within the document too as comments. This material needs to be translated into the language used during the workshop.
- **Participants Name Tag Template**, partners need to add there the participants information, download it, and print it.
- **STECCI PPT template**, this is the PowerPoint presentation with a general overview and information of the STECCI project, which needs to be translated and adapted to the event, by adding and removing information.
- **STECCI Certificate of Participation Template**, this is a template, which partners can update with the participants information and share it with them in the end of the event with the consortium logos.
- **STECCI List of Participants Template**, this the empty template that can be printed and used at the event. The participants should choose and sign if they consent to be taken **pictures of them. After the event, the signed participation list will be uploaded in each pilot folder on EMDESK.**
- **STECCI SLs Agenda Template**, there are two templates: one for internal use (with internal information) and one for external use, which can be sended to participants or printed out for the workshop. This document needs to be translated into the workshop language.
- **STECCI SLs Documentation Template**, which will be filled out carefully and uploaded to EMDESK. Based on this template a summary shall be compiled and sended to the participants latest three weeks after the workshop.

Fig. 3 Path and templates on the project's database EMDESK

All materials were designed and produced by the WP5 leader Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI GMBH). Pilot leading partners were asked to translate to their local language, in case needed.

REFERENCES

- **Deliverable 5.1** STECCI Social Innovation Labs – Methodology & Handbook (March 2024)
- **Deliverable 7.1** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (December 2023)